

PROFESSIONAL ENGLISH PROFICIENCY OF MEDICAL STUDENTS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Annotation. This article discusses the level of mastery of professional English for students studying in the medical field, existing problems in this regard and ways to overcome them. The author justifies the need for students to master this language in depth, since modern medical literature, international protocols and scientific articles are mainly in English. During the study, problems such as difficulties in memorizing medical terminology, limitations in understanding scientific texts, problems in expressing opinions freely in oral and written speech, and the lack of textbooks were identified. To solve them, proposals were put forward, such as the ESP model, interactive methods, multimedia technologies, the creation of modern textbooks, the use of English in practical classes, and the establishment of interdisciplinary cooperation. The article emphasizes the importance of modernizing medical education and achieving global competitiveness through the development of professional English.

Keywords: professional English, medical students, ESP, medical terminology, educational issues, interactive methods, multimedia technologies, interdisciplinary integration, practical training, global competitiveness.

In today's era of globalization and rapid development of information technologies, English is widely used not only as a means of international communication, but also as the main professional language in science, education, technology, and especially in the field of healthcare. In particular, almost all advanced scientific articles, modern textbooks, clinical research results, and international protocols written in the field of medicine are published in English. Recommendations of major organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO), the American Medical Association (AMA), and the European Society for Clinical Practice are also formalized in English.

Therefore, the need for students studying in the medical field to master the English language in depth and thoroughly, especially professionally oriented medical English, is increasing day by day. This plays a direct and important role not only in their academic activities, but also in their subsequent international practice, working with foreign scientific literature, participating in conferences, and mastering various medical technologies.

This thesis provides a comprehensive analysis of the level of professional English language proficiency of medical students, the main problems they face, and effective proposals for eliminating existing problems. Through interviews with students, oral and written questionnaires, as well as observations during the lesson, the following problems were identified:

1. Difficulty remembering medical terminology.

Tibbiyot tilining o'ziga xos xususiyati – uning murakkab, ko'p qismlardan iborat atamalarga boyligidir. Latinchaga asoslangan so'zlar, qisqartmalar va ko'p ma'nolilik talabalarda o'rganish jarayonida tushunmovchiliklar keltirib chiqaradi.

2. Limitations in understanding scientific texts written in English.

Many students, despite having grammatical knowledge, have difficulty understanding complex structures in scientific style, medical articles, article structure, and statistical data.

3. Problems in using oral and written speech in a professional context.

Students cannot confidently use their knowledge and skills when performing tasks such as speaking to a patient in English, explaining symptoms, describing a disease, or providing medical advice.

4. Lack of educational literature and methodological guides.

Many educational institutions still lack modern professional English textbooks and interactive resources. And the available materials are often theory-oriented and not closely linked to practice.

These problems not only complicate the educational process, but also negatively affect the training of globally competitive personnel in the medical field. Therefore, a fundamental revision of the system of teaching professional English is necessary.

Suggestions for troubleshooting:

1. Introducing the ESP (English for Specific Purposes) approach.

In this model, English is taught in a way that is not general, but specifically structured for the medical field, focusing on industry terminology. Through ESP, students learn to perform specific professional tasks in English.

2. Implementing interactive and communicative methods.

Through medical role-playing, clinical case discussions, and patient-doctor simulations, students are encouraged to actively participate and develop professional speaking skills.

3. Use of multimedia and digital technologies.

The introduction of English video lessons on medical topics, podcasts, mobile applications, interactive tests, as well as clinical exercises based on virtual reality into the learning process will increase student motivation.

4. Creating modern and practical textbooks.

It is necessary to develop English language materials, dictionaries, and exercise books that are appropriate for students' level and used in a medical context, in collaboration with local and foreign experts.

5. Conducting practical training in English.

By completing certain parts of clinical classes, laboratory work, or practical assignments in English, language use in a real-world context is achieved.

6. Strengthening collaboration between teachers and medical professionals.

Interdisciplinary integration is achieved by jointly developing curricula between English language teachers and medical professors.

Medical students who have mastered professional English will be able to actively participate in international cooperation as modern doctors in the future, will be aware of the latest scientific innovations, and will have the opportunity to improve their skills abroad. This is an important factor not only in their personal success, but also in increasing the competitiveness of our country's medical system.

Therefore, improving the process of teaching professional English in the medical field is one of the urgent tasks of today. In this regard, positive results can be achieved by studying advanced foreign experience, applying modern technologies, and harmonizing the national education system..

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